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ОРГАНИЗАЦИИ И УПРАВЛЕНИЯ ПРЕДПРИЯТИЕМ НЕФТЕГАЗОВОЙ
ПРОМЫШЛЕННОСТИ УЗБЕКИСТАНА** <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7994270>**АННОТАЦИЯ**

В данной статье освещается правовая база, создающая необходимые условия для инновационной деятельности и коммерциализации ее результатов в Узбекистане. Приведена информация о финансовых и нефинансовых инструментах стимулирования инноваций и выявлены некоторые проблемы в механизме реализации инновационных процессов в нефтегазовой отрасли. В заключении даны предложения по формированию инновационной политики в нефтегазовой отрасли республики на основе определенных принципов, направленных на создание благоприятных условий для широкого внедрения в производство инновационных методов управления.

Ключевые слова: управление, модели управления, методология управления, деятельность предприятия, инновации, нефть, газ, нефтегазовый комплекс, нефтегазовая отрасль, инновационное развитие.

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AND MANAGING AN ENTERPRISE IN THE OIL AND GAS INDUSTRY OF
UZBEKISTAN****ABSTRACT**

This article highlights the legal framework that creates the necessary conditions for innovation and commercialization of its results in Uzbekistan. Information is provided on financial and non-financial instruments for stimulating innovation and some problems are identified in the mechanism for implementing innovation processes in the oil and gas industry. In conclusion, proposals are given on the formation of an innovation policy in the oil and gas industry of the republic based on certain principles aimed at creating favorable conditions for the widespread introduction of innovative management methods into production.

Key words: management, management models, management methodology, enterprise activity, innovations, oil, gas, oil and gas complex, oil and gas industry, innovative development.

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BOSHQARISHNING INNOVATION USULLARINI YOQISHNING SAMARALI
SHAKLLARI****ANNOTATSIYA**

Ushbu maqolada O'zbekistonda innovatsiyalar va uning natijalarini tijoratlashtirish uchun zarur shart-sharoitlarni yaratuvchi qonunchilik bazasi yoritilgan. Innovatsiyalarni rag'batlantirishning moliyaviy va nomoliyaviy vositalari to'g'risida ma'lumot berilgan va neft-gaz sanoatida innovatsion jarayonlarni joriy etish mexanizmida ayrim muammolar aniqlangan. Xulosa sifatida ishlab chiqarishga innovatsion boshqaruv usullarini keng joriy etish uchun qulay shart-sharoitlar yaratishga qaratilgan muayyan tamoyillar asosida respublika neft-gaz sanoatida innovatsion siyosatni shakllantirish bo'yicha takliflar berildi.

Kalit so'zlar: menejment, boshqaruv modellari, boshqaruv metodologiyasi, korxonalar faoliyati, innovatsiyalar, neft, gaz, neft-gaz kompleksi, neft va gaz sanoati, innovatsion rivojlanish.

Introduction. The development of the oil and gas industry in Uzbekistan is taking place in parallel with significant organizational and economic transformations, which create a fertile ground for the development of production, as well as the widespread use of innovative technologies. The need to implement innovative processes in the oil and gas industry is associated, first of all, with the main problem of the economy - the rational use of limited resources to meet the growing needs of society. At the same time, an equally important prerequisite for innovative development is that today, in the context of globalization and a fundamental change in the world market conditions, competition is intensifying, and it is innovation that is the most effective means of competition, as it leads to the creation of new needs, to cost reduction. products, to increase volumes and improve production efficiency, which, in turn, affects the attraction of investments. Recognizing the effectiveness and high importance of innovation, it should be noted that the transition to the accelerated development of innovation requires the creation of a new organizational and economic mechanism. In other words, competition alone is not enough to launch the innovation process, competition is only the cause, the source of innovation processes, and more conditions are needed to promote their development. Such conditions, first of all, are organizational structures, specific forms and methods of management, as well as legal norms, with the help of which innovative projects will be implemented. In this regard, the issues of studying the organization and management of innovative processes, the formation of a mechanism for the introduction of innovative technologies, which receive much attention in the scientific economic literature, become relevant. At the same time, the changes taking place today in the world economy, an even greater demand for innovations, determine the improvement of the mechanism for introducing innovative technologies into the economy, in particular, the mechanisms for increasing innovative activity.

Analysis of literature on the topic. The founder of the theory of innovation is J. Schumpeter, who in his work "The Theory of Economic Development", published in 1912, considered innovation (new combinations) as a means of entrepreneurship for profit [20].

One of the first researchers of innovation problems in Russia was N.D. Kondratiev. He is famous for the fact that for the first time in his work "Large cycles of the conjuncture" he introduced the concept of "long wave" in relation to innovations that characterize the impact of radical innovations on world industrial development. He attributed such innovations: the invention of steam engines, the idea of building a railway, electric power and the automotive industry. [14] Currently, there is no generally accepted definition of innovation in the scientific literature. Analysis of the above definitions of the term "innovation" allows us to state that three points of view are widespread. First, innovation is identified with innovation, novelty. The second point of view, innovation is seen as a process of creating new products, technologies, innovation in the field of organization, economics

and production management. The third one is innovation as a process of introduction into production of new products, elements, approaches that are qualitatively different from the previous counterpart.

F. Pikson believes that innovation is a set of technical, industrial and commercial activities that lead to the emergence of new and improved processes and equipment on the market. Russian scientist V.P. Vlasov notes that "innovation" means the commercialization of the results of creative work, including in the humanitarian fields of knowledge, sold on the market for goods and services. In the world economic literature, "innovation" is interpreted as the transformation of potential scientific and technological progress (STP) into a real one, embodied in new products and technologies. In accordance with international standards, innovation is defined as the end result of innovative activity, embodied in the form of a new or improved product introduced to the market, a new or improved technological process used in practice, or a new approach to social services. The subjects of the innovation process are divided into innovators, early recipients, early majority and laggards. Innovators are generators of scientific and technical knowledge. These may be individual inventors or research organizations. They are interested in receiving a part of the income from the use of inventions. Entrepreneurs who are the first to master the innovation and seek to obtain additional profit by promoting innovation to the market as soon as possible act as early recipients. They were called "pioneer organizations". The early majority are firms that are the first to introduce an innovation in production, which provides them with additional profit.

According to I.G. Ushachev, I.S. Sandu V.G. Savenko, the effectiveness of innovation activity depends on the opportunities for the formation and development of innovation potential in the country as a whole, in each region, industry, sub-sector, enterprise.

Research Methodology The research is based on a general scientific methodology that involves the use of a systematic approach to problem solving. In the course of the study, various methods were used: observation, system analysis, economic and statistical analysis, expert assessments, monographic, etc. Analysis and results of the study from the standpoint of modern management theory are practically any processes and phenomena occurring in the state, the economy as a whole or a separate enterprise, carried out under the influence of the functioning of a certain type of mechanism. In the economic literature, there are several approaches to the interpretation of the concept of "management mechanism", the study of which made it possible to determine the essence and main aspects of the mechanism for managing innovation activity. The mechanism for managing innovation and introducing innovative technologies is an integral part of the economic mechanism, which should be understood as a set of specific forms and methods of management, organizational structures, legal norms, through which the actions of economic laws are implemented, a continuous process of reproduction is maintained, and macroeconomic balance is achieved at various levels. and in various macroeconomic systems.

The mechanism of the system for introducing innovative technologies is a system that includes two subsystems: organizational and economic mechanism. The organizational mechanism for managing the system of introducing innovative technologies consists of such elements as innovative marketing, administrative methods of state regulation of the national innovation system, and innovation clusters. The economic mechanism of the system for the introduction of innovative technologies is a set of methods and forms of influence on the economic interests of producers in order to increase the efficiency of the technologies being introduced. These methods of influence include: strategic planning; financing of subjects of innovative activity; lending; insurance of economic risks in the innovation sphere; pricing; relationships of business entities with suppliers and consumers; taxation; customs and tariff regulation of technology export-import. It should be noted that the organizational and economic mechanism operates in a certain regulatory and legal sphere, with the help of which the economic laws operating in specific conditions are implemented, and the process of reproduction in the national innovation system is ensured.

The key element in the mechanism for the implementation of innovative projects is the infrastructure of the innovation process, which is based on technology transfer centers, innovation and technology centers, technology parks and high-tech territories, R&D support funds, start-up and

venture financing funds, centers for training specialized personnel for information support of innovation and others

The Government of Uzbekistan has introduced both financial - grants, tax incentives, venture financing, and non-financial instruments to stimulate innovation - technology transfer centers, technology parks, the annual Innovation Fair. Their value is difficult to overestimate. For example, the annual republican fair of innovative ideas and projects, aimed at creating conditions for improving the technological level and competitiveness of domestic production, stimulating the development and implementation of research, development and technological projects in production, provides great opportunities for developing contacts between developers of innovative technologies with manufacturing companies. The results of fairs of innovative ideas, technologies and projects testify to a significant economic effect. In general, within the framework of the I-IX fairs, about 4,200 innovative ideas and technologies were presented, more than 4,000 contracts were concluded for a total of 144 billion 100 million soums. As noted, the republic pays special attention to stimulating innovation, the main forms of which are tax incentives, concessional lending, state grants, etc. A good example of comprehensive support and stimulation of active entrepreneurship, the accelerated development of science and innovation is the adoption of the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated January 22, 2018 No. UP-5308, according to which, for a period up to January 1, 2023, from paying all types of taxes and mandatory payments, with the exception of unified social payment, the following are exempted: emerging venture funds that co-finance high-tech entrepreneurial start-up projects; high-tech start-up projects co-financed from venture funds; research institutions, innovation centers, design bureaus on income received from the sale (transfer for use) of their own new technologies to entrepreneurs; organizations for the transfer of new technologies to domestic entrepreneurship in terms of income from this activity [6]. In addition, in order to create conditions for the further effective introduction of innovations in industries and sectors of the economy, research organizations are exempted until January 1, 2022 from customs duties (excluding customs clearance fees) for imported scientific equipment, components, consumables, reagents, software according to the lists approved in the prescribed manner. Research organizations, in terms of their core activities, are also exempt from all types of taxes and mandatory contributions, with the exception of contributions to the off-budget Pension Fund under the Ministry of Finance of the Republic of Uzbekistan, with the targeted use of the released funds for material incentives for their employees [3].

Conclusions and suggestions. Many more examples of the positive impact of the existing mechanisms for introducing innovations can be cited, but with large positive shifts in the organization and management of innovation processes, the development of innovation infrastructure, some gaps are also found. For example, a full-fledged innovation infrastructure should consist of such elements as a service system for innovative firms that carry out project examination, consulting, engineering, audit, advertising and other services, as well as various forms of entrepreneurship training in the scientific and technical field (educational institutions, special courses, departments, seminars, symposiums, etc.). Many of the above exist in our country, but their activities are defective and inefficient. This is due, first of all, to the lack of effective tools for financing scientific research, including incentives for enterprises in the real sector of the economy to participate in the implementation of scientific, applied and innovative projects and developments. The lack of investments, scientific connections, qualified personnel and low motivation, the lack of effective mechanisms for interaction between the state and the business sector of the economy are common reasons that hinder innovation. Based on the foregoing, the innovation policy in the oil and gas industry of the republic should be carried out on the basis of:

- strategic planning of the main directions of industrial development of scientific and technological achievements with the subsequent formation of a model of innovative development of industries;
- expanding opportunities for access to investment flows directed to the development and implementation of innovative ideas and technologies in the agricultural sector;

- increasing the level of development of the infrastructure of the innovation process, including the system of information and consulting support for producers, as well as training;
- further development of research potential based on the creation of a system of comprehensive support for the innovation activities of research institutions;
- improvement of the regulatory and legal framework that ensures the attraction of investments (including foreign ones) in the development and implementation of innovative ideas and technologies.

In general, the system for organizing and stimulating innovation in the oil and gas industry of our country should be aimed at public and private partnerships and include the following forms: tax and customs incentives, subsidies, loans, venture financing, contracts and orders in the field of research and development. - design work, information support, integration of science, education and business.

References:

1. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On measures to improve the coordination and management of the development of science and technology" dated August 7, 2006;
2. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On additional measures to stimulate the introduction of innovative projects and technologies into production" dated July 15, 2008;
3. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the Program of measures for the implementation of the most important projects for the modernization, technical and technological re-equipment of production for 2009-2014" dated March 12, 2008, etc.
4. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated April 27, 2018 No. PP3682 "On measures to further improve the system for the practical implementation of innovative ideas, technologies and projects."
5. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated May 7, 2018 No. PP-3698 "On additional measures to improve the mechanisms for introducing innovations in the industry and the economy."
6. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated 05.05.2018 No. PP3697 "On additional measures to create conditions for the development of active entrepreneurship and innovation."
7. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated July 14, 2018 No. PP3855 "On additional measures to improve the efficiency of commercialization of the results of scientific and scientific and technical activities."
8. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated January 22, 2018 No. UP-5308 "On the State Program for the Implementation of the Action Strategy in five priority areas of development of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2017-2021 in the Year of Support for Active Entrepreneurship, Innovative Ideas and Technologies".
9. Avsyannikov N.M. Innovation Management: Textbook. – M.: INFRA-M, 2002. – 295 p.
10. Valenta F. Management of innovations. – M.: Progress, 1985.
11. Innovation management: Textbook for universities / S.D. Ilyenkova, L.M. Gokhberg, S.Yu. Yagudin and others; Under. ed. prof. S.D. Ilyenkova. - 2nd ed., revised. and additional - M.: UNITI-DANA, 2003. - 343 p.
12. Kondratiev N.D. Selected writings. - M.: Economics, 1993. - S. 47.
13. Novikov V.M. Organizational and economic mechanism of innovative development of agriculture // Avtoref. dis. on sois. uch. step. Dan. Voronezh, 2013.
14. Santo B. Innovation as a means of economic development / Per. with Hungarian. – M.: Progress, 1990. – 376 p.
15. Utkin E.A., Morozova N.I., Morozova G.I. Innovation management. – M.: Akapis, 1996, p. 10.

16. Umarov I., Saidkarimova S., Oblokulova Sh. Analysis of indicators of the innovative potential of industrial enterprises // Scientific electronic magazine “Economics and innovative technologies”. No. 4, July-August, 2015
17. Fatkhutdinov R.A. Innovation management: Textbook for universities. 5th ed. - St. Petersburg: Peter, 2005. - 448 p.
18. Schumpeter J. Theory of economic development. - M.: Progress, 1982. -S. 169-170.
19. Implementation of project management in the oil and gas industry of Uzbekistan
20. Candidate of Economics, Professor Khairova D.R., Akhmedova Sh.K. Materials of the international scientific and technical conference "Innovative activity in science and education - a key factor in the development of the oil and gas industry", November 3, 2022, Tashkent
21. Implementation of project management in the Oil and Gas Industry of Uzbekistan Ph.D. in Economics, Professor Khairova D.R., Lecturer Akhmedova Sh.K. International scientific and practical online conference on the topic "Actual problems of business development and entrepreneurship in the digital economy" at the Higher School of Business and Entrepreneurship under the Ministry of Economic Development and Combating Poverty of the Republic of Uzbekistan, December 23, 2022, Tashkent.
22. <https://nuz.uz/nauka-i-tehnika/22991-h-respublikanskaya-yarmarkainnovacionnyh-idey-tehnologiy-i-proektov.html>.
23. <http://academy.uz/ru/news/>
24. stat.uz

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